

Development of an Assessment and Evaluation Model for Learning in the Eyes Learning Evaluation Lecture

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Abstract

One of the important components and stages that must be taken by lecturers to determine the effectiveness of learning. The results obtained from the evaluation can be used as considerations for lecturers in improving and perfecting learning programs and activities. The terms used in the evaluation system, namely measurement, assessment, and evaluation. The research method uses the RnD method. The model used is ADDIE. The result of the research is that the ADDIE model has a positive and significant influence on students' understanding of the learning evaluation course. This is evident from the results of repeated measures analysis and paired samples t-test, which show that there is a significant positive effect of the application of the ADDIE model on increasing student competence in the limited and expanded trials.

Keywords

Learning Evaluation, Development, Assessment Model

1. Introduction

In Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, especially in Article 1 paragraph 16, education evaluation is an activity of controlling, guaranteeing, and determining the quality of education for various components of education at every path, level, and type of education as a form of accountability for the implementation of education. In addition, in article 58, the evaluation of student learning outcomes is carried out by educators to monitor the process, progress, and improvement of student learning outcomes on an ongoing basis. Therefore, in the learning system, evaluation is one of the important components and stages that must be taken by lecturers to determine the effectiveness of learning. The results obtained from the evaluation can be used as considerations for lecturers in improving and perfecting learning programs and activities.

The term assessment (assessment) is defined by Stiggins [1] as an assessment of the process, progress, and student learning outcomes (outcomes). Meanwhile assessment is interpreted by Kumano [2] as "The process of Collecting data which shows the development of learning". Thus it can be concluded that assessment is the right term for assessment of student learning process. However, although the student

learning process is an important thing that is assessed in the assessment, the learning outcome factor is also not ruled out. Gabel [3] categorizes assessments into two major groups, namely traditional assessments and alternative assessments. Assessments that are classified as traditional are true-false tests, multiple-choice tests, complete tests, and limited-answer tests. Meanwhile, the alternative assessments (non-test) are essays/descriptions, practice assessments, project assessments, questionnaires, inventories, checklists, peer/peer assessments, self-assessments, portfolios, observations, discussions, and interviews (interviews). Wiggins [4] states that assessment is a tool that chronologically assists teachers in monitoring students. Therefore, then Popham [5] states that assessment should be part of learning, not an integral part. Resnick [6] states that in essence the assessment focuses on the assessment of the student learning process. In this regard, Marzano et al. [7] stated that in revealing students' mastery of concepts, the assessment not only revealed the concepts that had been achieved, but also about the development process of how a concept was obtained. In this case the assessment can not only assess student learning outcomes and processes, but also their learning progress.

The instructional process is a system. The concept of systems is used in various areas of life. This is to state that each object or event cannot stand alone, but is supported by other parts. Each of these parts has a function, so that if put together will get maximum results in accordance with what is planned.

Richey, Rita C., Klein, James D., Tracey, Monica in Suparman [8] state that the model represents reality by displaying structures and actions to express the idealization and view of a reality. "models imply are a representation of reality presented with a degree of structure and order, and models are typically idealized and simplified view of reality". The model itself has two categories, namely: micro morphs and paramorphism. The definition of micro morphs is a model in the form of an imitation, both an object and a computer simulation or a miniature of an object with a predetermined scale. Paramorphs are symbolic descriptions that usually use verbal descriptions. Examples of paramorphism are a) conceptual model b) procedural model c) Suparman [9] mathematical model.

Conceptual models are general and abstract theoretical descriptions to describe views of reality, synthesis and supported research by experience or limited data. The procedural model shows the steps in doing a job, for example the steps of instructional design, research and development cycle. while the mathematical model is in the form of a formula that describes the relationship between various components or factors. Suparman [10] explains that the model is a representation of reality that describes the structure and order of a concept and displays one of the following four forms: verbal or conceptual descriptions, steps of activities or procedures, physical or visual replicas, equations or formulas.

Nowadays, information and communication technology products in the form of mobile communication devices have become primary need since they offer a new paradigm in connectivity, communication, and collaboration in our daily lives. They allow people to use both in the office, at home, or during their trip. They influence wide sectors of our lives including in the field of education[11].

Instructional theories, beneficial for authoring learning resources, can be model using ontologies, as sets of rules for arranging activities and, more important in this case, learning resources in an LMS [12]. A Learning Management System is a web-based software application that is designed to handle learning content, student interaction, assessment tools and reports of learning progress and student activities Learning content that is online is accessed through an LMS, which allows students to see and interact with learning tools via web browsers using any operating system, computer or mobile devices. Learning Management Systems are also platforms that

include learning systems, course management systems, content management systems, portals, and instructional management systems. Learning Management Systems represent an evolution from the processes and systems developed by certain institutions to register students on specific courses and keep records of students' activities. Various learning choices developed to enable students to take online courses, sometimes as part of the formal curriculum and sometimes due to the need for institutional certification. LMS can also help students to access learning information via course guidelines, uploading assignments and downloading marks, active interactions between students and lecturers, interactions between students, interactions between students and learning tools, sharing knowledge, and taking online exams and quizzes [13].

2. Research Method

This research method uses the RnD (Research and Development) method. Research and development is a development model based on an industrial model, where the results of this research are used to design new procedures and products, then systematically tested in the field, evaluated, and refined until they meet the requirements. specified criteria such as effectiveness, quality, or meeting standards. The instructional design model uses ADDIE for product development. Robert Marible Branch [14] states: ADDIE is an acronym for Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. ADDIE is a product development concept. The ADDIE concept is being applied here for constructing performance-based learning. The educational philosophy for this application of ADDIE is that intentional learning should be student centred, innovative, authentic, and inspirational.

Figure 1. ADDIE Concept

In this study there are several characteristics. The characteristics of the product that will be developed is the Development of an Assessment and Evaluation Model of learning.

3. Result and Discussion

The results of the research and discussion consist of: (1) the results of the validation of experts and practitioners (2) the results of the limited trial, (3) the results of the expanded trial, and (4) the discussion of the research results.

Expert and Practitioner Validation Results Prior to testing, the ADDIE prototype and model tools were validated by experts and practitioners through focus group discussions (FGD). The results of the validation of 3 experts (measurement, learning

technology, and language and indicate that the ADDIE model prototype is feasible to be tested with an average score greater than 3.25 (very good) and a level of consistency (c) between validators is equal to or greater 0.70 This means that the prototype of the ADDIE model can be tested.

After the ADDIE model prototype was validated by experts and practitioners and declared feasible to be tested, then it was tested in a limited scope (3 Respondents). This limited trial is intended to determine: (a) the results of the assessment of the effectiveness of the ADDIE model, (b) the empirical results.

After being declared effective in the test limited trial, the ADDIE model was tested on a wider scope. The purpose of the expanded trial is the same as the purpose of the limited trial, namely to determine: (a) the results of the assessment of the effectiveness of the ADDIE model, (b) the results of observing the implementation of the ADDIE model, The test results of the ADDIE model, both limited and expanded, show that the ADDIE model is effective in improving the competence of understanding evaluation.

The results of the research, both in the limited and expanded trials, are logical, because the ADDIE model helps students: (1) understand learning objectives, (2) understand and work on structured assignments, (3) conduct selfassessments, (4) conduct peer assessments, and (5) find feedback to improve learning. In addition, the results of this study also support the results of Black and Wiliam's (1998a) research which states that the use of well-designed and implemented assessment as and for learning (formative assessments) can increase student competence, with effect sizes ranging from 0.4 to 0.7.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, conclusions and suggestions can be drawn as follows. There are six components that must exist in the ADDIE model to improve student competence in learning evaluation learning. The six components are: goals, structured tasks, self-assessment, peer assessment, observation of student activities, and feedback. Objectives include learning objectives, indicators, and success criteria. Structured assignments consist of sample questions and completion, structured task questions, and assessment rubrics. The six components interact with each other in the learning process to improve the learning process and outcomes in the evaluation course. The ADDIE model can effectively improve students' accounting competence in learning evaluation learning. This is evident from the results of repeated measures analysis data analysis and paired samples t-test which shows that there is a significant positive effect of the application of the ADDIE model on increasing student competence in the limited and expanded trials, with $p(0000) < (0.05)$.

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